

**INFLUENCE OF SOCIOECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESIDENTS
ON THE MAINTENANCE OF MASS HOUSING SCHEMES IN ILORIN
METROPOLIS, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Socioeconomic background of residents is an important factor in housing provision for any population in the developed world. It is often believed that it influences certain behaviours. However in Nigeria, housing provision is usually done by the providers without the input of residents' background thereby leaving a gap on its influence on housing, most especially housing maintenance. This study therefore examines the effect of socioeconomic characteristics of residents on housing maintenance in mass housing schemes in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara state, Nigeria. The study is quantitative in nature and both primary and secondary data were utilized. It employed multistage sampling technique and a total of 1125 questionnaires constituting 27% of the sample frame were administered to household heads selected from public, private as well as public-private-partnership mass housing schemes. Data obtained were analysed with descriptive statistics, while pearson-product moment correlation (PPMC) was employed to analyse the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics of residents and housing maintenance. The study found out that the residents majorly aged 51 years and above, had HND/1st /postgraduate degree (81.0%) and are primarily government workers (37.0%). The highest monthly income (27.7%) was however above #121,000. There is a high (strong) positive correlation between socioeconomic characteristics of residents and maintenance of houses ($r=0.725$) implying socioeconomic characteristics are the determinants of housing maintenance in the area. The study therefore suggests among others that the socioeconomic characteristics of inhabitants of mass housing schemes should be factored both at the design and maintenance stage so as to ensure that the house will be sustainable in future.

Keywords: Influence, socioeconomic characteristics, residents, maintenance, mass housing schemes.

Introduction

There is a universal shortage of decent and well-maintained dwelling units in the less developed countries, Nigeria inclusive. Rapid population growth and urbanisation are creating escalating demands for added living spaces (Bajere, 1996; Amuda and Adewoye, 2020) and there is a wide gap between housing needs and efforts to increase the number and quality of available units.

According to Amuda and Adewoye (2020), there are several factors that cause the inadequacy of housing in the country among which is the high rate of unmaintained houses due to lack of maintenance culture. Houses are ageing, and in many cases, there is the need to repair, so as to prolong the life span. Research conducted by Cobbinah (2010) showed that over 80% of public residential buildings had maintenance problems and this is because, housing maintenance is not factored into housing production. Great emphasis is placed on the gap between housing demand and supply, but little attention is paid to the maintenance of existing housing stock (Obeng-Odoom and Amedzro 2011).

Mass housing schemes are repetitive housing solutions that have emerged as a complement of urban regeneration to cover the acute shortage of housing in cities. They are meant to solve housing problems; however, the country is far from achieving the goal (Ibimulua and Ibitoye, 2015; Adebimpe and Peters, 2018); the maintenance of mass housing schemes is often neglected and despite the pivotal roles of housing in socioeconomic development and the life of the people, majority of mass housing schemes are provided without the input of user.

In the developed world, socioeconomic characteristics of residents is an important factor in housing planning, most especially, mass housing schemes. According to Waziri et al (2014), socioeconomic characteristics of residents help policymakers and professionals in the building industry to consider the maintenance of mass housing schemes by carefully considering sustainable building materials for maintenance purpose. However, in Nigeria, there is a gap on the role of socioeconomic characteristics in mass housing schemes maintenance. Studies are either concentrated on mass housing scheme quality (Mbazor, 2018; Blome, 2010; Adeoye, 2018); delivery strategies (Cobbinah, 2010; Odunjo, Oladimeji and Okanlawon, 2015) and security measures (Foluke et.al, 2019) to mention a few. Thus, there is the need to find out the influence of socioeconomic characteristics of residents on housing maintenance in Nigeria. This study therefore examines the effects of socioeconomic residents on maintenance in mass housing schemes in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara state, Nigeria. This is with a view to improving the living conditions of the houses. In order to do this, a hypothesis was set for the study and this states that:

Ho- There is no relationship between socio-economic characteristics of residents and maintenance of mass housing schemes in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara state, Nigeria.

The Study Area

Ilorin is the capital of Kwara State in the middle belt of Nigeria. It is located on longitude 4° 27' 38.05" E, 4° 39' 15.11" E, and latitude 8° 23' 05.57"N, 8° 34' 09.39"N. It has a population of 908,490 as of 2011 making it the 13th largest city in Nigeria with a land area of 765 km sq. and density of 1,188/km square (Odunjo, Oladimeji and Okanlawon, 2015). It lies in the savannah climatic region and has three local governments which are Ilorin East, Ilorin West and Ilorin South as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 : Map of Ilorin metropolis

Source: GIS Laboratory, Urban and Regional Planning Department, (LAUTECH 2021)

Figure 2: Map of Mass Housing Schemes in Ilorin metropolis
 Source: GIS Laboratory, Urban and Regional Planning Department, (LAUTECH 2021)

Ilorin is the largest city in Kwara state which is strategically located as the gateway between the north and southwestern Nigeria. This has led to the amalgamation of citizens from these regions who are predominantly of Islam (north) and Christianity (west) faiths respectively. This, therefore, contributes to making Ilorin, a confluence of cultures, populated by Yoruba, Hausa, Fulani, Nupe, Igbo, Baruba and other ethnic groups as well as foreign nationals with significant Christianity and Islamic faiths.

Recently, more people from western and eastern Nigeria previously resident in northern Nigeria migrated to Ilorin, because of insecurity challenges due to insurgencies. This coupled with the progress made by

the previous Governments of the State in their effort to bring investors to the state led to a relative increase in the economic activities of the city. There are a lot of mass housing schemes in Ilorin metropolis such as Harmony estate, Royal valley estate and Mandate estate etc as shown in Figure 2

Methodology

The population consists of all the mass housing schemes or the estates in Ilorin metropolis, while the unit of analysis is the house. All the houses constructed under the mass housing programme in the three local government areas of Ilorin, inclusive of Federal and State governments, Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) and the Organised Private Developers constituted the population for the study. Ilorin city is selected because it is the capital of Kwara State in which the State Government has given the highest priority in its mass housing programme.

However, the sample frame consists of houses completed (and occupied) by each of the stakeholders in the provision of housing. The total number of houses sold amounts to 4,166 which is the sample frame for the study. Multistage sampling technique was employed and the first stage was the stratification of the metropolis into local government areas. These are Ilorin West, Ilorin South and Ilorin East. The second stage involved the identification of mass housing schemes in each of the local government area. According to Kwara State Housing Corporation and

reconnaissance survey carried out, Federal government has two estates, which is the Low-cost estate and Ministerial housing estate. Kwara state government has eleven, PPP has four, while the Private sector has a total of eight estates.

In the third stage, information was collected on the details of the mass housing projects from the PPP and the private sector and in the last stage, the sample size was selected. To have a good representation of each of the housing delivery strategies, twenty-seven per cent (27%) of the houses were randomly sampled from the sample frame leading to a total of 1,125 samples for consideration. . Since there are different house types in the area, in order to ensure that the samples selected are representative of the population from which they are drawn, Equal Probability of Selection Method (EPSEM) was applied. The twenty-seven per cent sample from each of the housing delivery strategy was applied to the different house types in each estate or mass housing project. A sample was then randomly taken by drawing papers scripted with the number of houses contained in hats for each house type and in each housing delivery strategy. Thereafter, others were systematically selected at an interval of one after the other. Thus, the breakdown of the samples from each house type was 271, 923, 454, 146 and 4 houses in the 1,2,3,4,5-bedroom types of houses respectively. Data obtained were analysed using descriptive

statistics such as frequency counts and percentages, while Pearson-Product moment correlation was employed to analyse the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics of residents and housing maintenance.

Findings and Discussion

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents

More than three-tenths (33.1%) of the respondents were 51 years and above. This was followed by 41-50 years (28.3%) and 31-40 years (20.2%). Respondents that were 21-30 years account for 16.4%, while, below 20 years constituted 2.0%. The implication of this is that majority of the respondents are adults and mature and it is expected that reliable information will be obtained from them regarding housing maintenance in the area.

However, the distribution of educational background of respondents as shown in Table 1 indicates that those with no formal education accounted for 4.9%, primary education were 0.3%, while 7.3%, 9.5% and 78.0% of respondents had modern/secondary education, Nursing certificate/NCE/OND and HND/1st degree/Postgraduate degree respectively. Thus, it can be inferred from the analysis that the education of the people in the mass housing schemes of Ilorin metropolis is largely high. This is not unexpected taking into consideration the fact that the

residents of mass housing schemes in Ilorin like any other city are mostly elite. This tends to suggest that the three mass housing delivery strategies provided housing mainly for the highly educated people, this is good as it will enable the respondents to position the existing situation of housing maintenance in their respective estates.

Furthermore, analysis shows that the respondents are majorly public sector (37.0%) workers. Those who work in the private sector accounted for 24.7%, while self-employed constituted 23.0%. Retirees/Pensioners were however 4.6% of the total respondents sampled, while the unemployed were 10.7%. The bulk (27.7%) of the respondents were collecting above N121,000 monthly, while the minimum salary of workers in the area was N31,000-N60,000 which is a little bit higher than the minimum wage in Nigeria. Thus, it is inferred that the majority of the residents are high-income and middle workers by Nigeria Standard.

Most households had a membership size of 4-6 persons (58.2%) followed closely by below 3 persons (24.1%) and 7-10 persons per house (12.4%) as shown in Table 1. The tendency towards large family size is indicated by the fact that a significant proportion (1.2%) of households had membership sizes of 11-13 persons and 14 persons and above (4.1%). Thus, there is the possible influence of family size on maintenance of the

house in which the size of family will dictate the amount to spend on housing maintenance as observed by Odunjo (2014)

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics Background of Respondents

S/N	Variables	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	
A	Age (years)	18 years and below	21	2.0
		19-30 years	171	16.4
		31-40 years	211	20.2
		41-50 years	295	28.3
		51 years and above	345	33.1
		Total	1043	100.0
B	Educational Background	HND/1 st degree/Postgraduate degree	814	78.0
		Nursing/NCE/OND	99	9.5
		Modern/ Secondary education	76	7.3
		Primary school	3	0.3
		No formal education	51	4.9
		Total	1043	100.0
		C	Employment Status	Public sector
Private sector	258			24.7
Self employed	240			23.0
Retiree/pensioners	48			4.6
Unemployed	111			10.7
Total	1043			100.0
D	Monthly Income	N30,000 and below	34	3.3
		N31,000-N60,000	181	17.4
		N61,000-N90,000	113	10.8
		N91,000-N120,000	116	11.1
		N121,000 and above	289	27.7
		Others	310	29.7
		Total	1043	100.0
E	Household Size	Below 3 persons	251	24.1
		4-6 persons	607	58.2
		7-10 persons	129	12.4
		11-14 persons	13	1.2
		14 persons and above	43	4.1
		Total	1043	100.0

Source: Authors' field survey (2021)

Housing Maintenance

The maintenance level of houses in the area was measured by the condition of houses at the time of fieldwork. Hence, housing condition was measured using five (5) variables which constitute the major elements of a building and are foundation, wall, roof, floor, and painting/tile which constitutes finishes. (Table 2)

Table 2: Housing Condition of Mass Housing Schemes in Ilorin

S/ N	Variabl es	Very good		Good		Fair		Poor		Very poor		Missing value		Total	
		Fre q. (N)	Per c. (%)	Fre q. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fr eq. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fr eq. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fr eq. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fr eq. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fre q. (N)	Pe rc. (%)
1.	Foundat ion	448	43.0	259	24.8	309	29.9	6	0.6	0	0	21	2.0	104	10
2.	Wall	273	26.2	314	30.1	379	36.3	57	5.5	0	0	20	1.9	104	10
3.	Roof	255	24.4	309	29.6	284	27.4	16	1.6	0	0	28	2.7	104	10
4.	Floor	224	21.5	441	42.3	303	29.1	43	4.1	0	0	32	3.1	104	10
5.	Painting /Tile	214	20.5	392	37.6	240	23.0	16	1.5	4	0.4	33	3.2	104	10

Source : Authors' field survey (2021)

Analysis shows that the bulk (43.0%) of foundation in the area were in very good condition, while there is none in very poor condition. This implies that foundations of houses in the area are relatively maintained and this could be due to the educational background of the

residents as well as the fact that they are mostly employed. However, walls in the area were majorly in fair condition (36.3%) which may be that only foundation is maintained at the expense of wall in order to avoid structural failure of the building. Furthermore, the dominant roof condition in the mass housing schemes was good (29.6%) as well as floor (42.3%), and painting /tile (37.6%).

Relationship between Socioeconomic Characteristics of Residents and Housing Maintenance

Variables were identified and used as socio-economic characteristics; they are age, educational level, employment status, monthly income and household size. Also, five (5) variables were identified for the maintenance of buildings. These variables are the maintenance of; foundation, wall, roof, floor, painting/tile. To make these variables suitable for Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis, they were summarized into one composite variable through the use of average computation. This was done and two (2) composite variables of socio-economic characteristics and maintenance level of houses were statistically obtained. They were thereby correlated and the result is contained in Table 3.

Table 3: Relationship between Socio-economic Characteristics of Residents and Maintenance of Houses

		Correlations	
		Socio-economic characteristics	Maintenance of houses
Socio-economic characteristics	Pearson Correlation	1	0.725**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	642	585
Maintenance of houses	Pearson Correlation	0.725**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	585	937

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Authors' Computation, (2021)

According to the table, with a correlation coefficient of 0.725, it is observed that there is a high (strong) positive correlation between the socio-economic characteristics of residents and the maintenance of houses. This implies that the socio-economic characteristics of residents influence the maintenance of houses considerably. Moreover, with a p-value of 0.000, it is also observed that there is a significant relationship between socio-economic characteristics of residents and maintenance of houses at $p < 0.05$ confidence level in the mass housing scheme in Ilorin metropolis.

Conclusion

The study has examined the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics and the maintenance of houses in mass housing schemes in

Ilorin metropolis. It shows that socioeconomic characteristics of residents are predictors of housing maintenancen and have positive effects on the overall housing condition and level of maintenance.

Based on this conclusion, it is suggested that the socioeconomic characteristics of residents should be factored into housing planning both at the design and maintenance stage in order to provide houses that will be sustainable in future. Also, government and stakeholders involved in the provision of mass housing schemes should be using sustainable building materials that will be durable and easy to maintain. The stsakeholders of the mass housing schemes should provide the necessary assistance to the residents in the maintenance of infrastructure in the mass housing schemes.

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